

MULTIFACETED PERSPECTIVE ON COENURUS CEREBRALIS IN TURKEY IN THE LAST 5 YEARS: A REVIEW OF CLINICAL, MOLECULAR, AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL STUDIES

Keywords

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ABSTRACT

Coenurus cerebralis, the larval stage of *Taenia multiceps*, is a significant neurotropic cestode that causes severe neurological disorders in both domestic and wild animals and poses zoonotic threats. In recent years, the number of studies on this parasite in Türkiye has increased, addressing coenurosis from clinical, molecular, serological, pathological, and ecological perspectives. This review systematically evaluates scientific publications from 2019 to 2025, providing a contemporary overview of the epidemiology, diagnostic methods, host diversity, and control strategies concerning *C. cerebralis* infections in Türkiye. The reviewed studies report the presence of multiple genetic haplotypes within the same host, seasonal and demographic risk factors affecting prevalence, and advanced diagnostic approaches such as PCR-based techniques, Western blot analysis, and promising biomarkers like GFAP and S100B. Cases observed in wild species such as mountain goats also suggest that physiological stress may trigger latent infections. Surgical interventions and serological screenings demonstrate practical applicability in field settings. This review underscores the urgent need for extensive molecular surveillance, diagnostic tools based on recombinant antigens, and integrated control programs involving both domestic and wild hosts. Strengthening interdisciplinary collaborations is critical to limit the spread of the disease and mitigate its impact on veterinary public health.

INTRODUCTION

Coenurus cerebralis, the larval form of *Taenia multiceps*, is a significant parasitic infestation with zoonotic potential that can result in fatal outcomes. While adult *T. multiceps* parasites reside in the small intestines of carnivores such as dogs, jackals, and foxes¹, a wide range of intermediate hosts including sheep, goats, cattle, buffalo, yak, pigs, deer, horses, camels, and even humans can become infected^{2,3,4}. Sheep become infected by ingesting the parasite eggs disseminated through the feces of infected dogs on pasture⁵. After the eggs reach the CNS via the bloodstream, the cysts mature with well-formed scolices within 3 months and reach 5–6 cm in diameter after 7–8 months. The definitive host excretes three to four gravid proglottids containing eggs within 40–60 days after ingesting the cysts^{1,6}.

Coenurosis is a globally prevalent disease and a major cause of economic loss in livestock. In sheep and goat herds, its impact is especially severe. Moreover, ingestion of contaminated food or water containing *T. multiceps* eggs by humans can lead to zoonotic infections, highlighting the public health significance of this parasite^{7,8}.

This review aims to bring together scientific studies conducted in Türkiye over the past five years on *Coenurus cerebralis* from diverse angles, offering a comprehensive and up-to-date perspective on its epidemiology, pathogenesis, diagnostic approaches, economic implications, and control strategies.

FINDINGS

In a case from Elazığ, the brain of a 1-year-old Akkaraman sheep, which exhibited symptoms such as dullness, reluctance to move, drooling, dizziness, frequent convulsions, ataxia, and decreased appetite, was examined post-slaughter. Seven cysts were identified. Çelik et al. (2025) molecularly analyzed each *Coenurus cerebralis* cyst extracted from the sheep's brain. The mt-CO1 gene region was amplified via PCR, sequenced, and phylogenetically evaluated. A total of 20 polymorphic sites were identified among the isolates. Only one matched a previously known haplotype, while the remaining six formed unique haplotypes. This was the first documentation in Türkiye of multiple *C. cerebralis* haplotypes co-existing within a single host. The study made a significant contribution to the molecular epidemiology and genetic monitoring of coenurosis⁹.

In Iğdır province, Akkuş and Oğuz (2024) conducted postmortem brain examinations on 300 sheep with neurological symptoms and identified *C. cerebralis* cysts in 82% (n = 246) of the animals, most frequently in the left cerebral hemisphere. This suggested a directional tendency in parasite migration, consistent with reports of left-hemisphere dominance in the literature. Of the 243 macroscopically confirmed cases analyzed by molecular methods, all tested PCR-positive for the COX1 gene, yielding a 100% diagnostic success rate. Sequence analysis revealed that two of the

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three isolates matched 100% with Chinese reference strains, while one showed 99.19% similarity. The results indicated both phylogenetic similarity with Chinese strains and the presence of local genetic variants. Higher infection rates in male and under-1-year-old sheep were associated with factors such as age, sex, and grazing behavior. Seasonally, prevalence peaked in spring, summer, and autumn, reflecting environmental transmission Dynamics¹⁰.

In another study from Iğdır, Kızıltepe and Ayvazoğlu (2022) examined the brains of 1,688 slaughtered sheep with neurological symptoms and detected *C. cerebralis* cysts in 28.1% (n = 474) of cases. The highest prevalence (46%) occurred in the 8–12-month age group, with male sheep more commonly affected (32.6%). The seasonal distribution revealed a peak in October (46.6%), indicating the influence of age, sex, and seasonal factors on infection rates. The authors emphasized that regular anthelmintic treatment for dogs and limiting slaughter to official abattoirs are essential control measures¹¹.

Taş et al. (2023) evaluated the surgical removability of *C. cerebralis* cysts from sheep brains. Trepanation and excision procedures were successfully performed on 20 infected sheep, and the animals regained normal motor and metabolic functions post-operatively. Biochemical parameters measured before and after surgery (TP, ALP, BUN, AST, CK, LDH, RBC, WBC, Hb, and Hct) confirmed the reliability of the surgical intervention. The findings suggested that surgery could be an effective and feasible treatment strategy under field conditions¹².

Uztimur and Dörtbudak (2023) investigated the use of brain-specific biomarkers GFAP and S100B in goats infected with *C. cerebralis*. The levels of these markers were significantly elevated in infected animals. Histopathological and immunohistochemical analyses revealed inflammation triggered by TNF- α and DNA damage marked by 8-OHdG. These findings suggest that GFAP and S100B could serve as useful in vivo diagnostic indicators and may help monitor brain damage caused by *C. cerebralis* biochemically¹³.

Tüfekçi et al. (2022) reported a central nervous system infection due to *C. cerebralis* in a pregnant Anatolian wild goat found in the Aladağlar Wildlife Development Area in Yahyalı district, Kayseri province. Initially presenting with lethargy and loss of appetite, the animal developed typical neurological signs such as ventroflexion, wall-seeking behavior, unilateral head tilt, bilateral blindness, and lethargy. Despite supportive treatment, the animal died after 16 days. Necropsy revealed a large cyst with multiple scolices between the two cerebral hemispheres and a dead fetus in the uterus. This case highlighted the potential for physiological stress (e.g., pregnancy) to activate latent infections and underscored the parasite's presence and pathogenicity in wildlife¹⁴.

In a study by Çelik et al. (2024), specific antigenic markers from cyst fluid were evaluated for the serological diagnosis of *C. cerebralis* in sheep. Antigens were separated using SDS-PAGE and transferred to nitrocellulose membranes for Western blot (WB) analysis. Eight protein bands (12–180 kDa) were identified across 40 infected serum samples. Of these, the 24 and 68 kDa bands showed high antigen-antibody reactivity, suggesting strong potential as diagnostic markers. The results indicated that these antigens could support the development of more specific recombinant antigen-based diagnostic tools⁶.

DISCUSSION

The findings from studies conducted in Türkiye over the past five years indicate that *Coenurus cerebralis* is not limited to domestic species such as sheep and goats, but is also circulating in wildlife populations, revealing a broader ecological distribution than previously understood. The case of a pregnant Anatolian wild goat reported by Tüfekçi et al. (2022) suggests that physiological stress (e.g., pregnancy) may trigger latent infections, and that the parasite can cause clinical disease in wildlife hosts as well.

Molecular analyses by Çelik et al. (2025) demonstrated the coexistence of multiple haplotypes within a single host, indicating high genetic diversity within *T. multiceps* populations. Similarly, Akkuş and Oğuz (2024) reported close phylogenetic relationships with Chinese isolates while also identifying local variants. These results underline the need for continuous molecular surveillance and genotyping to monitor parasite dynamics.

The 24 and 68 kDa protein bands identified by Çelik et al. (2024) using Western blot exhibited strong antigenic sensitivity and appear to be promising targets for serological diagnosis. Moreover, Uztimur and Dörtbudak (2023) found elevated levels of brain-specific biomarkers GFAP and S100B in infected goats, suggesting the potential of these non-invasive biochemical parameters in in vivo diagnosis. Additionally, the successful surgical excision of cerebral cysts in sheep by Taş et al. (2023) highlighted the feasibility of curative intervention, particularly in high-value animals.

These findings emphasize the necessity of a multidisciplinary perspective in evaluating *C. cerebralis* infections, incorporating classical parasitology with molecular, serological, and ecological dimensions. They also call for a revision of existing diagnostic, surveillance, and control strategies.

Limitations

This review has several limitations. It includes a total of seven peer-reviewed studies, comprising six original research articles and one case report. A systematic review protocol (e.g., PRISMA) was not applied, instead, a selective narrative review approach was adopted based on methodological quality, scientific relevance, and novelty of findings. Only studies conducted in Türkiye and published in Turkish or English were included, while publications in other languages were excluded. Moreover, grey literature sources such as theses, congress abstracts, and non-peer-reviewed reports were not considered. Therefore, the findings presented here do not claim to represent the entire body of available literature. Nevertheless, the selected studies provide a reliable, up-to-date, and multifaceted perspective on *Coenurus cerebralis* infections in Türkiye.

CONCLUSION

Studies conducted in Türkiye over the past five years demonstrate that *Coenurus cerebralis* infections have been approached from multiple perspectives, including clinical, epidemiological, molecular, and serological angles. The presence of infections in both domestic and wild animals highlights the zoonotic potential and environmental

transmission of the parasite. The detection of multiple haplotypes within a single host also reveals intriguing evolutionary dynamics, necessitating the development of more sensitive and precise diagnostic and control tools. Molecular and biochemical diagnostic methods, such as Western blot, PCR, and biomarker assays, offer promising avenues for early and accurate diagnosis. If adapted to field conditions, these methods could improve practical disease detection. The demonstrated success of surgical treatment also provides a practical alternative for managing valuable livestock.

Effective control of *C. cerebralis* requires regular antiparasitic treatment, monitoring of canine reservoirs, exclusive slaughter in licensed abattoirs, and prevention of environmental contamination. Furthermore, expanding molecular characterization efforts, mapping local variants, and conducting risk analyses are essential steps toward establishing a national control strategy.

Future studies should involve larger sample sizes from diverse regions, the development of recombinant antigen-based diagnostic kits, and the implementation of active wildlife surveillance systems. These efforts would significantly contribute to the management of *C. cerebralis* infections from both veterinary public health and animal welfare standpoints.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The author declares that there are no financial or personal conflicts of interest that could have influenced the work reported in this article.

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